

COMPARATIVE DAMAGE ANALYSIS OF VARIOUS OPEN CROSS-SECTION GLARE COMPOSITE COLUMNS

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ABSTRACT

The subject of this study is comparative damage analysis of thin-walled open-cross section composite columns subjected to compression. Experimental and numerical study is performed for 7-layered glass reinforced aluminum laminates (GLARE). Composite specimens were subjected to compressive laboratory tests by means of static testing unit that provided displacement control loading. Simultaneously, numerical model with adequate boundary conditions was prepared to investigate the post-buckling response and damage modes of GLARE members. Failure analysis was carried out separately for aluminum and fiber-reinforced composite plies. Isotropic aluminum material was analyzed by equivalent stress magnitude (EQVS) calculated by Huber-Mises-Hencky (H-M-H) criterion. Failure simulation of fiber-reinforced composite layers included Hashin and Puck failure criteria application. Additionally, progressive failure analysis was introduced to assess the failure propagation after the onset of material failure. The damage evolution law after failure initiation was performed in FEA by the material property degradation method (MPDG). Results of numerical simulations were found to be in good agreement with experimental results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced composites are recognized as one of the most commonly applied structural materials that have been increasingly used in recent years. Significant developments are observed in aerospace, automotive, sport equipment, civil and transport industries [1–3]. Therein, multi-layered composite structures tend to replace traditional materials such as steel or aluminum. This is due to the growing demand for lightweight and high strength materials that needs to meet high requirements of modern industries [4,5].

One of the type of fiber-reinforced composite is glass reinforced aluminum laminate (GLARE). Considered GLARE structure is a hybrid composite that consists of alternating thin layers of aluminum alloy sheets and unidirectional glass fiber-reinforced prepregs [6]. Such plies combination guarantees improved damage and fatigue tolerances when compared to other materials on a unit weight basis [7]. Glass fiber-reinforced aluminum laminates provide also high strength and stiffness of the structure when subjected to different loading conditions. Furthermore, depending on the fiber alignment, fiber-reinforced composites can be manufactured to be stiffer in one specific direction which finds many industrial applications [8,9].

Worldwide increasing trend of composite materials application affects future directions of engineering design and this has inspired research activities to investigate its mechanical behavior under specific loading conditions [10,11]. In literature, one can find various papers concerning theoretical and experimental studies of different thin-walled composite structures subjected to compressive loading [12–15]. With regards to comprehensive damage and fracture analysis, separate failure modes of various composite material constituents are already identified [8] but there is still considerable uncertainty with regard to their specific interaction. The aim of this research is to perform failure analysis of various open-cross section columns subjected to compression test and to investigate various damaged modes.

2 SUBJECT OF CONSIDERATION

The subject of this research is a thin-walled open-cross section column made of glass reinforced aluminum laminate (GLARE). Comprehensive numerical and experimental study was performed for different thin-walled, open cross-section profiles that included top hat sections.

Metallic layer in the analyzed FML sample is an aluminum alloy - 2024 T3. For composite layers a unidirectional fiber-reinforced prepreg TVR 380 M12 26% R-glass is applied. Thickness of a single aluminum layer equals to 0.3 mm whereas the thickness of a single prepreg layer after curing is equal to ca. 0.25 mm. Mechanical properties of aluminum and glass-epoxy prepreg constituents were adopted from manufacturer data and gathered in Table 1.

Al 2024-T3	[GPa]	TVR 380 M12/26%/R- glass	[GPa]
E	72	$E_{L(1)}$	46.43
G	$E/2(1 + \nu)$	$E_{T(2)}$	14.92
$R_{0.2}$	359×10^{-3}	$E_{(3)}$	14.92
E_{tang}	$E \times 10^{-3}$	G_{12}	5.233
		G_{23}	3.570
		G_{13}	5.233
		ν_{12}	0.269
		ν_{23}	0.400
		ν_{13}	0.269

Table 1: Mechanical properties of FML constituents.

For each 7-layered GLARE columns, the 3/2 laminate lay-ups were considered and different stacking sequences were distinguished based on fibers alignment in the composite layer. GLARE composite columns were manufactured by autoclaving technique that provided the high quality of multi-layered laminates.

2 EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL TESTS

Experimental failure test was performed in laboratory by a universal electromechanical strength-testing machine of Instron upgraded with Zwick/Roel control software. Considered double column static testing unit had a maximum capacity of 200kN. Applied screw type testing machine provided a displacement control loading of 1 mm/min. Experimental tests were carried out for considered thin-walled top-hat-section columns (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Experimental tests for top-hat section specimens.

In Finite Element Analysis the boundary conditions (BC) were consistent with assumed simply supported type which was modelled by displacement prevention at loaded edges. Thus, nodes located along these edges were constrained in the direction perpendicular to the profile walls. For the upper edge, despite lateral deflection constrains, specific nodes were also coupled to guarantee the same displacement in the axial direction (Fig. 2). More details of BC description for considered thin-walled section is given in Ref. [16].

Figure 2: Boundary conditions applied to top-hat-section columns

3 FAILURE ANALYSIS

Discrete model was generated in FEM commercial software package Ansys® by means of implemented structural shell element SHELL181. Numerical computations were performed to predict the failure of the 7-layered GLARE structure in a buckling and post-buckling state. Analysis was carried out separately at each layer of the laminate.

Initially, the strength of layers modelled as isotropic aluminum material were judged by equivalent stress magnitude (EQVS) calculated by Huber-Mises-Hencky (H-M-H) criterion. Subsequently, numerical failure simulation of fiber-reinforced composite layers included Tsai-Wu, Hashin and Puck failure criteria application. This enabled to perform composite failure analysis wherein the matrix and fiber failure were considered separately [17]. Based on considered criteria, failure factors (FF) were determined to assess the potential failure of the structure in the full load range. Maps of computed failure factors were mapped onto composite structure, which allowed one to indicate particular areas of the laminate which are greatly exposed to damage. Results of numerical simulation were judged against experimentally damaged specimens.

Damage in composite laminates seldom occurs abruptly but tends to be progressive with substantial damage gradually induced throughout the material [18]. Hence, an attempt was also undertaken to investigate a progressive failure and create a composite degradation model [19].

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initially, Huber-Mises-Hencky (H-M-H) criterion was used to calculate maps of equivalent stresses (EQVS) distribution. This enabled predicting failure initiation at the region, where EQVS exceeds material yield limit. Based on maps of equivalent stresses, failure initiation in aluminum layers is observed at the middle length of web-flange joint and along rib's free edges (Fig. 3a). This is due to highest flexural state that accumulates in this region. Similar region of laminate failure is noticed in experimentally damaged specimens (Fig. 3b). Detailed analysis of stress tensor elements in FEA is required to detect component stresses that contributes to material failure.

Figure 3: Aluminium layers of top-hat section judged by H-M-H criterion (a) and compared with experimentally damaged specimen (b).

Subsequently, various failure criteria were used to calculate failure factors in composite plies. For the purpose of this study, results of Hashin and Puck failure criteria for matrix damage were particularly taken into consideration. By means of these criteria, FF were calculated and mapped onto the profile geometry in order to indicate particular regions greatly exposed to failure (Fig. 4). Failure factors were calculated for the load case that corresponded to structure load-carrying capacity.

As a results, both considered failure criteria exhibit similar damage modes which implies a good compliance of failure criteria implementation in damage analysis of the composite matrix. Agreement within results was also obtained for other failure criteria (Tsai-Hill, Hoffman, Tsai-Wu) determined for composite layers under load carrying capacity. Each criterion predicted similar maps of failure factors in the considered load case. Nevertheless, Hashin and Puck failure criteria were found to provide the highest accuracy in terms of detecting regions of laminate failure (Fig. 3). Herein, maximum values of FF were detected close to the column's mid-length where the highest stress concentration was expected. This was in-line with abovementioned failure analysis performed in aluminium layers. Similar regions of specimens damage were obtained in experimental failure tests carried out for top-hat sections (Fig. 3b).

Figure 4: Composite layer failure analysis by Hashin (a) and Puck failure criteria (b).

Another stage of the research included the progressive damage analysis (PDA). For that purpose, the Hashin criterion was applied to predict the onset of material damage. The damage evolution law after failure initiation was performed by the material property degradation method (MPDG) available in FE software. Thus, according to specific guidelines and based on the damage variables (df, dm) the stiffness was gradually reduced once the failure was initiated [19]. As an example, results for composite layer with stiffness degradation factor equal to unity is shown in Fig. 5. According to revealed scale from FEM, progressive failure models included the considerations of the damage status i.e. 0 - undamaged, 1 - damaged, 2 - completely damaged.

Figure 5: Numerical progressive failure analysis (a) compared with the experimentally damaged specimen (b).

Numerical progressive failure analysis allowed to assess the failure propagation after the onset of material failure. Damaged status was displayed at the load corresponding to structure load-carrying-capacity. Based on the results of such FE simulation, failure is initiated at the mid-length of the column and propagates symmetrically from ribs' free edges towards the center of the profile' web. Complete damage status is observed across the web's length and it propagates towards both ends of the profile. Comparative analysis of numerical results aimed also to verify the fracture modes of the columns that show similar pattern as experimental tests. Importantly, the implementation of progressive failure analysis in the modelling process increased substantially the computation time required to solve the appropriate equilibrium equations for GLARE damage analysis.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, comparative damage analysis was performed to investigate failure performance of GLARE thin-walled members. Physical specimens were subjected to compressive laboratory tests by means of universal testing machine that provided displacement control loading. Numerical model with appropriate boundary conditions was created in FEM by shell type element to investigate the post-buckling response and damage modes of GLARE members. Herein, selected failure criteria were used to predict damage of top-hat-section columns subjected to compression.

In aluminum layers, equivalent stresses mapped onto the profile geometry indicated the greatest susceptibility of failure at the middle length of web-flange joint. Failure initiation was observed at the region where EQVS exceeds aluminum yield limit. In composite plies, Hashin and Puck failure criteria were found to provide the highest accuracy in terms of detecting regions of laminate failure. Maximum values of failure factors were mapped close to the column's mid-length where the highest stress concentration is expected. Similar regions of specimens damage were obtained in experimental failure tests.

Presented FE simulation included also the attempt of implementation the progressive damage analysis. For that purpose, Hashin criterion was used to indicate the onset of material failure in GFRP

plies. The damage evolution law was performed by the material property degradation method (MPDG). Such analysis allowed also to detect regions of laminate failure initiation at the mid-length of the columns and its propagation symmetrical from ribs' free edges towards the center of the profile' web.

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